

Bioremediation of Cd^{II} from aquatic systems by Bermuda grass matrix

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Abstract : This work was undertaken to explore low cost and efficient sorbents for the removal of cadmium(II) from aqueous solution. For this purpose dried Bermuda grass was taken. The optimum experimental conditions were established for maximum removal of Cd^{II} from the aqueous solution. Besides studying the effect of temperature, pH, contact time, concentration of metal ion and adsorbent doses the adsorption kinetics and equilibrium were also investigated. Kinetic studies suggested that the adsorption follows second order reaction. Equilibrium data were analyzed using Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm isotherms.

Keywords : Adsorbent, cadmium, dried Bermuda grass, Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms, intra-particle diffusion, thermodynamics.

Introduction

Cynodon dactylon (Family : Poaceae, dhub in Hindi, Bermuda grass in English) a creeping herb rooting at the joints with smooth upward stem. The roots are whitish, tough and creeping, almost woody with smooth fibers. Leaves tapering to a sharp point, ribbed with smooth sheath and hairy stipules. Flowers are purplish arranged in two close alternative rows in equally crowded 4 or 5 terminal, linear spikes and blooming in the month of August to September¹. Although some trace metals are considered as essential plant nutrients, but many heavy metals are of considerable health and environmental concern because of their toxicity and bio accumulative behavior²⁻⁴. Pb^{II}, Ni^{III}, Fe^{III} and Cr^{III} are especially common metals that tend to accumulate in organisms, causing numerous diseases and disorders⁵. Most health and safety agencies identified cadmium and cadmium compounds to be carcinogenic. Cadmium can cause a variety of effects such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, muscle cramps, salivation, sensory disturbances, liver injury, convulsions, shock and renal failure. After ingestion or inhalation, cadmium accumulates in the kidney, liver, lungs, and gastrointestinal tract where it causes progressive toxic effects, including cancer and renal damage⁶. Cadmium exists as Cd²⁺ ions in the drinking water. Cadmium hydroxide [Cd(OH)₂] is the dominant species at a pH greater than 10. Cadmium get introduced in water bodies from

smelting, metal plating, cadmium-nickel batteries, phosphate fertilizer, mining, pigments, stabilizers, alloy industries and sewage sludge. The harmful effects of cadmium include a number of acute and chronic disorders, such as "itai itai" disease, renal damage, emphysema, hypertension, and testicular atrophy. The drinking water guideline value recommended by World Health Organization (WHO) is 0.005 mg Cd/L. Numerous processes exist for removing dissolved heavy metals, including ion exchange, precipitation, phyto extraction, ultra-filtration, reverse osmosis and electro dialysis⁷⁻¹⁰. The use of alternative low cost materials as sorbents for the removal of heavy metals has been emphasized recently. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the efficiency of adsorbent dried Bermuda grass (DBG) for the removal of cadmium(II) ions in aqueous solution. The effects of parameters such as initial cadmium(II) ion concentration, pH, adsorbent dosages, contact time, and temperature were studied using batch technique.

Results and discussion

Analytical measurements :

Scanning Electron Microscopy :

The scanning electron microscopy image (Fig. 1) shows the surface morphology of DBG is coarse which binds with the Cd^{II} and the dark spots shows the large numbers pores present on the DBG surface, which helps in sorp-

tion of metal ion onto the DBG and makes the DBG a good sorption material. The post sorption SEM image shows the change in the morphology of DBG as shown in Fig. 1a.

Fig. 1. Scanning Electron Microscopy image of DBG.

Fig. 1a. Scanning Electron Microscopy image of DBG after sorption.

XRD spectral results :

The diffractograms of DBG (Fig. 2) shows that it is amorphous in nature and the presence of metal ion is represented by three sharp peaks whose position [$^{\circ}$ Th.] and d-spacing in [\AA] i.e. distance between the two layers of particles is given in Table 1.

FT-IR spectral study :

The Fourier transforms infra red spectroscopy surface characterization of DBG (Fig. 3) indicated the presence of 3417 cm^{-1} is for O-H stretching vibration; 2920 cm^{-1} is for C-H stretching vibration (CH_2); 2424 cm^{-1} is for C-H stretching vibration (Aldehyde); 2125 cm^{-1} is for alkyne mono substituted; 1868 cm^{-1} is for saturated, 5-member ring (Aldehyde); 1763 cm^{-1} is for saturated, acyclic; 1639 cm^{-1} is for N-H bending vibration primary; 1519 cm^{-1} is for C- NO_2 aromatic; 1384 cm^{-1} is for alkane gem di methyl; 1248 cm^{-1} is for N_3 stretching vibration azides; 1159 cm^{-1} is for OH bending C-O stretching (tertiary alcohol); 1036 cm^{-1} is for S=O stretching vibration; 898 cm^{-1} is for alkene; and other functional groups were able to bind with Cd^{II} and make DBG an excellent adsorption material.

Effect of variable parameters :

Effect of adsorbent dose :

The various doses of the adsorbent were mixed with the concentration of 5 mg/L of cadmium ion having concentration 5 mg/L , and the mixture was agitated in a mechanical shaker. The doses of adsorption varied in the range from 0.5 g to 2.0 g and the percentage of adsorption was determined by keeping all other factors constant

Fig. 2. The diffractograms of DBG through XRD.

Pos. (°2 Th.)	FWHM (°2 Th.)	d-spacing (Å)	Rel. int. (%)	Area (cts* °2 Th.)
42.0465	0.2342	2.14897	82.33	40.96
49.1055	0.3011	1.85531	100.00	63.96
55.5046	0.0816	1.65424	66.87	15.67

Initial concentration of cadmium ion :

The adsorption experiments were conducted keeping the initial concentration of cadmium ion in the range from 50 to 200 ppm, other factors being constant (Fig. 5) from this rate of adsorption was determined. The maximum

Fig. 3. Fourier transforms infra red spectroscopy surface characterization of DBG.

(Fig. 4). The increasing amount of adsorption with increasing dose adsorbent is due to availability of more binding sites.

adsorption of metal ion was at 50 ppm. This may be due to the non availability of binding sites for higher concentration of metal ion.

Fig. 4. Adsorbent dose vs % adsorption.

Fig. 5. Concentration vs % adsorption.

Contact time :

While keeping initial concentration, dosage and temperature constant, the removal of the cadmium ions in a single cycle was determined by the effect of contact between adsorbent and adsorbate (Fig. 6). The maximum adsorption of metal ion is at 120 min. With increasing contact time the binding sites of adsorbents are more exposed and therefore the formation of more bonds with the metal ion is possible.

Temperature :

In a thermo stated magnetic stirrer four different temperatures were fixed i.e. 30, 40, 50 and 60 °C for the adsorption experiments. The results were used to investigate the thermodynamics of the adsorption process and the equilibrium was attained at 30 °C. At higher temperature adsorption decreases (Fig. 7) and so it is an exothermic process.

Fig. 6. Time vs % adsorption.

Fig. 7. Temperature vs % adsorption.

Initial pH :

While carrying out the experiments particle size of the adsorbent, temperature and other factors were kept constant and the adsorption process was carried out in the range of pH 3 to 9 (Fig. 8). The required amount of HCl and NaOH solutions were added to maintain the pH of

could influence the adsorption capacity. The percentage of sorption increased due to the presence of ionic functional groups. The adsorption of metal ion on the DBG does involve ion exchange mechanism. Due to the adsorption of cadmium ion through ion exchange mechanism by the DBG, there should be an influence on the

Fig. 8. pH vs % adsorption.

the medium and maximum adsorption was at pH 7. This indicates that the strong forces of interaction between the cadmium ion and the DBG i.e. either H⁺ or OH⁻ ions

metal ion adsorption while varying the pH. The positive ΔH° value was obtained, which indicates irreversible adsorption probably due to polar interaction^{11,12}. The other

Fig. 9. Langmuir adsorption isotherm profiles of Cd^{II} at different temperatures.

important factor which might contribute to the high adsorption of metal ions with increased pH, is the pH_{zpc} of DBG. At any pH below pH_{zpc} , the surface of metal oxides/oxyhydroxides is positively charged and at pH above pH_{zpc} the surface is negative. When the solution pH exceeded pH_{zpc} , the cadmium species are more easily attracted by the negatively charged surface of adsorbent DBG, favoring accumulation of cadmium species on the surface and thus promoting adsorption^{13,14}.

Zero point charge :

pH drift method was used to measure the pH at the potential of zero charge of the DBG (pH_{zpc}). 0.50 mg of the DBG was added to 50 mL of the solution. After stabilization the final pH was recorded. The pH of the solution was adjusted by using 0.01 M HCl or NaOH. The zero point charge of the dried Bermuda grass was determined and pH_{zpc} is 5.1.

Isotherms models :

Langmuir isotherm model :

The saturated monolayer isotherm can be represented as :

$$q_e = Q_m bC_e / (1 + bC_e) \quad (1)$$

The linearized forms of eq. (1) can be written as follows¹⁵ :

$$C_e/q_e = 1/bQ_m + C_e/Q_m \quad (2)$$

where q_e is the adsorption density (mg/g) at equilibrium of Cd^{II}, C_e is the equilibrium concentration (mg/g) of the Cd^{II} in solution, Q_m is the monolayer adsorption capacity (mg/g) and b is the Langmuir constant (L/mg) related to the free energy of adsorption. The values of Q_m and b were calculated from the slopes ($1/Q_m$) and intercepts ($1/bQ_m$) of the linear plots of C_e/q_e vs C_e (Fig. 9) and given in (Table 2) linear plots of C_e/q_e vs C_e shows that the adsorption isotherm of Cd^{II} on DBG follows the Langmuir isotherm model at all the four temperatures (303 K, 313 K, 323 K, 333 K). The value of Q_m 303 K indicates that the higher adsorption capacity of DBG at lower temperature.

Freundlich isotherm model :

Freundlich isotherm can be expressed as follows¹⁶ :

$$q_e = K_f C_e^{1/n} \quad (3)$$

The linearized form of eq. (3) can be written as follows :

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + (1/n) \log C_e \quad (4)$$

where K_f and n are Freundlich constants related to sorp-

Table 2. Isotherm parameters for Cd^{II} adsorption on DBG

Temp. (K)	Langmuir isotherm parameters			Freundlich isotherm parameters		
	Q_{max}	b	R^2	K_f	n	R^2
303	0.00325	0.00152	0.999	3.2885	1.0075	0.999

tion capacity [$\text{mg g}^{-1} (\text{mg L}^{-1})^{-1/n}$] and sorption intensity of adsorptions. The values of the K_f and n were calculated from the intercept ($\log K_f$) and slope ($1/n$) of the plots $\log q_e$ vs $\log C_e$ (Fig. 10) and presented in Table 2. Linear plots of DBG also fitted well in Freundlich isotherm model. The values of $n > 1$ indicates favorable adsorption condition^{17,18}.

Fig. 10. Freundlich adsorption isotherm profiles of Cd^{II} at different temperatures.

Adsorption kinetics :

Several kinetic models have been proposed to clarify the mechanism of a solute sorption from aqueous solution onto an adsorbent. The rate constant of adsorption was determined from the pseudo-first order rate expression¹⁹ eq. (5) given by Lagergren :

$$\ln (q_e - q_t) = \ln (q_e - k_1 t) \tag{5}$$

where q_e and q_t are the amount of Cd^{II} adsorbed at equilibrium and at time t (mg/g) respectively and k_1 (min^{-1}) is rate constant of adsorption. The values of K_1 and q_e^{cal} were calculated from the slopes ($-K_1$) and intercepts ($\ln q_e$) of the plots of $\ln (q_e - q_t)$ vs t (Fig. 11) respectively (Table 3).

Table 3. Kinetics parameters for Cd^{II} adsorption on DBG

Initial Cd ^{II} conc. (mg/L)	q_e^{exp}	Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order		
		q_e^{cal}	K_1	R^2	q_e^{cal}	K_2	R^2
5 mg	1.025	77.624	0.0023	0.999	1.621	51.118	0.999

The pseudo-second order sorption kinetics¹⁹ may be written as follows :

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 = t/q_e \tag{6}$$

where k_2 is the rate constant of sorption (g/mg min), q_e and q_t are the amount of Cd^{II} adsorbed at equilibrium and at time t (mg/g) respectively. The values of k_2 and q_e^{cal}

were calculated from the intercept ($1/k_2 q_e^2$) and slopes ($1/q_e$) of the plots of t/q_t vs t (Fig. 12) respectively (Table 3). From Table 3 it is clear that the values of regression correlation coefficient (R^2) are closer to 1 and the values of q_e^{cal} and q_e^{exp} are almost equal for the pseudo-second order kinetics model. Therefore it can be concluded that in present case the adsorption of Cd^{II} onto DBG follows pseudo-second order kinetics model.

Intra particle diffusion :

The mechanism of adsorption can be explained by inter particle diffusion model proposed by Morris and Weber²¹ which can be expressed by the following eq. (6).

$$q_t = K_d t^{1/2} + C \tag{6}$$

where q_e is the amount of Cd^{II} adsorbed (mg/g) and K_d is the rate constant in mg/g min^{-1} and $t^{0.5}$ is the square root of time. Fig. 13 shows two distinct regions : one with an initial linear portion which is due to the boundary layer effect²² and a second portion which is due to the intra-

Fig. 11. Pseudo-first order kinetics plot for adsorption of Cd^{II} ion on DBG (adsorbent dose : 2 g/L; pH : 7; Temp : 303 K).

Fig. 12. Pseudo-second order kinetics plot for adsorption of Cd^{II} ion on DBG (adsorbent dose : 2 g/L; pH : 7; Temp. 303 K).

particle diffusion effect²³. However, the fact that the line depicted in Fig. 13 does not pass through the origin

indicates that intra-pore diffusion is not the controlling step in the sorption of Cd^{II} by DBG^{24,25}. The value of the

Fig. 13. Intra-particle diffusion of Cd^{II} onto DBG.

rate constant K_d was calculated as 2.620 which gives indication about the mobility of the Cd^{II} towards the DBG.

Thermodynamic study :

To observe the effect of temperature on the adsorption of Cd^{II} on DBG, experiment were conducted at 303 K, 313 K, 323 K, 333 K. It was observed that adsorption

phase with an increase in temperature of the solution²⁶. Thermodynamic parameters such as $\ln b$ is the natural log of Langmuir constant, enthalpy (ΔH°), entropy (ΔS°) and Gibb's energy (ΔG°) were determined by eqs. (7)²⁷ and (8).

$$\ln b = \Delta S^\circ/R - \Delta H^\circ/RT \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (8)$$

where R is the gas constant (8.314 J/mol/K) and T is the temperature in K. ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔG° are changes in the enthalpy (J/mol), entropy (J/mol/K) and Gibb's energy (J/mol), respectively. The values of ΔH° and ΔS° were determined from the slope ($-\Delta H^\circ/R$) and the intercept ($\Delta S^\circ/R$) of the plots of $\ln b$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 14). The ΔG° values were calculated using eq. (9). The values of thermodynamic parameters are presented in Table 4. A negative value of ΔG° indicates that the adsorption process is spontaneous in nature. Negative values of ΔH° suggest that the adsorption is exothermic in nature. The negative value of ΔS° described the decrease in the randomness at the adsorbent-solution interface during the sorption. The ΔH° values obtained for adsorption of Cd^{II} on DBG which indicates that the physical as well as chemical sorption is taking place.

Fig. 14. The plot of $\ln b$ vs $1/T$ for adsorption of Cd^{II} on DBG (adsorbent dose : 2 g/L; pH : 7 contact time : 120 min).

was decreased on increasing the temperature, which indicates the low temperature favors Cd^{II} removal by sorption onto the DBG. This may due to this tendency for the Cd^{II} molecules to escape from the solid phase to the bulk

ΔH° (kJ/mol)	ΔS° (J/mol/K)	ΔG° (kJ/mol)			
		303 K	313 K	323 K	333 K
-42.435	-127.146	-3.335	-6.328	-9.519	-12.884

Experimental

Adsorbent :

All chemicals of analytical grade were used and were supplied by Merck Co. Ltd. The Bermuda grass was purchased from the local market, washed thoroughly with running tap water to remove mud and other impurities then it was thoroughly washed with double distilled water to remove all soluble impurities from it. Thereafter the material was dried in a hot air oven for 48 h at 80 °C. Then it was grinded thoroughly in a mechanical grinder (Philips) and passed it through 0.25 mm mesh size sieves and stored in air tight container for further use.

Batch adsorption process :

Stock solution of Cd^{II} (1000 mg/L) was prepared by dissolving requisite amount of cadmium chloride (Merck) into double distilled water from this solution number of solutions with concentration of cadmium as 5, 10, 50, 100, 150 and 200 mg/L were prepared with appropriate dilution. The pH of all these solutions was adjusted with the help of 0.1 M HCl and 0.1 M NaOH. The adsorption experiments were carried out in a batch process at 30, 40, 50 and 60 °C temperatures. The known weight adsorbent material was added to 50 mL of the metal ion solutions with an initial concentration of 5–200 mg/L. The contents were shaken thoroughly using a Magnetic stirrer (Remi India) rotating with a speed of 200 rpm. The solution was then filtered at preset time intervals and the residual concentration of cadmium ion was measured with the help of atomic absorption spectrophotometer (ECIL-4141).

Percentage of Cd^{II} adsorption and quantity of Cd^{II} adsorbed on adsorbent at the time of equilibrium (q_e) was calculated using eqs. (9) and (10) respectively.

$$\% \text{ Adsorption} = \frac{(C_0 - C_e)}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (9)$$

$$q_e = (C_0 - C_e) V/W \quad (10)$$

where C_0 and C_e is the initial and the equilibrium concentrations (mg/L) of Cd^{II} in solution, respectively, q_e is quantity of Cd^{II} adsorbed at the time of equilibrium (mg/g), V is the volume (L) of the solution and W is weight of adsorbent (g) taken for experiment.

Conclusion

The results of the study clearly demonstrate that DBG is a potential adsorbent for the removal of Cd^{II} from the aqueous medium. The optimum condition for the adsorption was found to be pH 7 and temperature 303 K. Equilibrium studies show that the adsorption of Cd^{II} onto DBG followed the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. Adsorption processes follows pseudo-second order kinetics, surface adsorption and intra-particle diffusion mechanism. The negative value of ΔH° and ΔG° indicates that the adsorption of Cd^{II} onto DBG was thermodynamically feasible, spontaneous and exothermic processes.

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References

1. S. Ravindra, "Medicinal Plants of India an Encyclopedia", Daya Publishing House, New Delhi, 2003, 79.
2. J. A. Omgbu and M. A. Kokogbo, *Environ. Int.*, 1993, **19**, 611.
3. A. A. Yusuf, T. A. Arowolo and O. Bomboso, *Food Chem. Toxicol.*, 2003, **41**, 375.
4. V. O. Ajibola and I. Ozigis, *J. Chem. Soc. Nigeria*, 2005, **30**, 62.
5. V. J. Inglezakis, M. D. Loizidou and H. P. Grigoropoulou, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2003, **49**, 261.
6. Darwish and Blake, *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, 2001, **16**, 799.
7. L. E. Applegate, *Chem. Eng.*, 1984, **64**, 91.
8. A. K. Sengupta and D. Clifford, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 1986, **20**, 149.
9. J. Geselbarcht, Micro Filtration/Reverse Osmosis, Pilot Trials for Livermore, California, Advanced water Reclamation in, Water Reuse, Conference Proceedings, AWWA, 1996, 187.
10. J. L. Schnoor, Remediation of Metals-Contaminated Soils and Groundwater Phytoremediation TE-97-01, Ground-water Remediation Technologies Analysis Center, Pittsburgh, 1997.
11. R. Sivaraj, C. Namasivayam and K. Kadirvelu, *Waste Manage.*, 2001, **21**, 105.
12. B. Stephen Inbaraj and N. Sulochana, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 2002, **9**, 201.

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13. Yupeng Guo, Jingzhu Zhao, Huizhang, Shaofeng Yang, Zichen Wang and Hongding Xu, *Dyes Pigments*, 2005, **66**, 123.
14. Nigamananda Das and Ranjit Kumar Jana, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2006, **293**, 253.
15. M. Ghoul, M. Bacquet and M. Morecellet, *Water Research*, 2003, **37**, 729.
16. A. Aklil, M. Mouflih and S. Sebti, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2004, **A112**, 183.
17. B. H. Hameed, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2009, **166**, 233.
18. B. H. Hameed, D. K. Mahmoud and A. L. Ahmad, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2008, **158**, 65.
19. M. Dogan, M. Alkan, A. Türkyilmaz and Y. Özdemir, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2004, **B109**, 141.
20. Y. Zhi-yuan and J. China univ, *Mining & Technol.*, 2008, **18**, 0437.
21. W. J. Weber and S. C. Morris (Jr.), *J. Sanit. Eng. Div. Am. Soc. Civ. Eng.*, 1963, **89**, 53.
22. J. Crank, "The Mathematics of Diffusion", Carlendon Press, Oxford, London, 1965.
23. G. McKay, M. S. Otterbern and A. G. Sweeney, *Water Research*, 1980, **14**, 15.
24. S. E. Ghazy and A. H. Ragab, *Indian J. Chem. Technol.*, 2007, **14**, 507.
25. S. Akhtar and R. Qadeer, *Adsorp. Sci. Technol.*, 1997, **15**, 815.
26. M. Jiag, Q. Wang, X. Jin and Z. Chem, *J. Hazard., Mater.*, 2009, **170**, 332.
27. B. K. Nandi., A. Goswami and M. K. Purkait, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2009, **161**, 387.

